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A Common Law Perspective on Space Law Methodology

Ben Sheridan¹

ABSTRACT

Common law is more than just the legal system that pervades much of the English-speaking world. It is a unique method of forming and applying law. Increasingly, the development of space law is shifting towards a civil law approach. Such a tendency has the dangerous potential to stifle the development of high-quality space law. This paper presents a common law perspective on the development of space law. In the first part, it demonstrates the civil law orthodoxy that exists in space law. In the second part, it sets out the distinctive structural features of the common law and demonstrates how they may be of use to space lawyers. Specifically, a common law approach can improve the fairness of decision-making, improve the law-making process, and enable more countries to contribute to space law. In the third part, it examines potential drawbacks of a common law approach and addresses those concerns.

KEYWORDS: common law, space law, civil law, decision-making

1. INTRODUCTION

Common law is the main legal system throughout much of the English-speaking world. Originally the legal system of England and Wales, it spread across the globe due through the influence of the British Empire.² It includes such countries as Australia, India, Malta, the United States (except state law in Louisiana and Puerto Rico), and Zimbabwe, to name just a few.³ Common law jurisdictions are identifiable by their distinctive characteristics. Foremost among these are: judge-made law, precedent, flexibility, case-based law-making, and published law-reports.⁴ By contrast, civil law, the other main type of legal system in the world, owes its roots to Roman law, specifically Emperor Justinian's *Corpus Juris Civilis*.⁵ In the 19th century, a number of national civil codes were promulgated, notably France's Napoleonic *Code Civil* in 1804 and Germany's *Bürgerliches Gestezbuch* ('BGB') in 1900. The drafters of civil codes aimed to create comprehensive documents to clearly set out the law. Unlike common law, civil law systems place less

¹ Space Court Foundation Intern, ben.sheridan@spacecourtfoundation.org

² Joseph Dainow, 'The civil law and the common law: some points of comparison' (1967) 15 American Journal of Comparative Law 3, at 424.

³ Sandra F. Joireman, 'Colonization and the Rule of Law: Comparing the effectiveness of common law and civil law countries' (2004) Political Science Faculty Publications, at 38.

⁴ Dainow (n 2), at 424.

⁵ *Ibid.* at 421.

importance on the doctrine of precedent and give their judges little power to change the law.⁶ Although being part of the same type of jurisdiction, civil law countries can have significant differences in their laws. By contrast, common law countries share much substantive law, and judgments in one common law country often examine the law in other common law jurisdictions. A persuasive judgment from one common law country even has a weak power of precedent in other common law countries.

Increasingly, both at the national level and international level, space law is adopting a civil law approach. This paper will identify flaws with this. Second, a number of structural advantages of common law will be examined and their potential utility in space law will be demonstrated. Notably, in terms of improving the quality of decision-making, elevating the quality of debate, and enabling more countries to contribute to space law. Finally, concerns regarding the adoption of this common law approach will be acknowledged and assuaged.

2. CIVIL LAW ORTHODOXY IN SPACE LAW

2.1 Domestic law

Across the world, academics and practitioners call for increased space law regulation.⁷ Through lobbying and advocacy, they seek to take advantage of the time and breathing space that humanity has now to develop laws to ensure that space is used in a manner that benefits humanity before industry lobbyists and vested interests distort the law-making process. Such an argument is attractive but marks an evolution in the development of space law. Domestic legislation used to have to catch up with technological agreements and international agreements. A good example of this is the passage in the UK of the Outer Space Act (OSA) in 1986 – 19 years after the Outer Space Treaty (the obligations from which the OSA sought to bring into domestic law). Recently, however, countries have passed laws regulating activities that have not yet occurred nor are likely to happen in the immediate future. For example, Luxembourg⁸ and the US⁹ have both legislated to create legal frameworks that regulate mining resources in space. The crucial point that these developments illustrate is that domestic space law is very unusual in that it is, in places, further ahead than the technology which might support the activities that it seeks to regulate.

2.2 International law

Harmonisation between countries' space law is increasingly breaking down. For example, the 2020 Artemis Accords have few signatories outside of Western countries.¹⁰ The long-term impact of such a break-down in consensus could well be a fracturing of goodwill and cooperation. This would be very problematic given that international agreements have recognised the importance of cooperation in space. For example, Article I OST requires states to “encourage international co-operation” with regard to scientific investigation.¹¹ Picker argues that what often sets a civil law approach apart from international law is that civil law typically develops by theory whereas international law develops by compromises between nations forced by

⁶ Francis Deak, ‘Place of the case in the common and the civil law’ (1933-1934) 8 *Tulane Law Review* 3, at 344.

⁷ See David A. Epstein, ‘Protecting the Cosmos: The Need to Define Celestial Bodies in the Outer Space Treaty’ (2023) 47 *Journal of Space Law* 2; Adriana ‘Ana’ Santana, ‘Options for a Liability Framework for Commercial Low-Earth Orbit Destinations’ (2024) 49 *Air and Space Law* (4/5).

⁸ Law of July 20, 2017 on the exploration and use of space resources. https://space-agency.public.lu/en/agency/legal-framework/law_space_resources_english_translation.html

⁹ US Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act of 2015, s.402. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/house-bill/2262>

¹⁰ Artemis Accords. <https://www.nasa.gov/artemis-accords/>

¹¹ *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.), Article I. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>

necessity.¹² Increasingly, however, space law is being developed by theory not necessity. The International Law Association (ILA) in its draft convention on dispute resolution mechanisms for space law has proposed that the International Court of Justice (ICJ) have jurisdiction over disputes between countries in space.¹³ Notably, there is no concept of *stare decisis* in the ICJ; indeed, its constitutive treaty explicitly precludes its decisions from having precedential value.¹⁴

3. LESSONS FROM COMMON LAW

3.1 *Quality of decision making*

Common law is created by judges' responses to specific facts in cases.¹⁵ This confronts judges with the immediate consequences of their decisions. For example, a legislator passing legislation on contract law will likely not have the same emotional response as, for example, Lord Reid in *Beswick v Beswick*,¹⁶ who, confronted with the reality of a "grossly unjust"¹⁷ quantum of damages, adopted a more flexible remedy to avoid injustice. The humanity of judges, therefore, is an important safety net. It ensures that the focus of the judgment is on the parties in the case. This becomes even more relevant for space law. The legislator passing the housing bill can hear testimonials from tenants, summon experts who have empirically analysed the impact of policies, and have a degree of first-hand experience. Much of this is absent from space activities. Therefore, none of the present safeguards that legislators can use to bring stakeholders into the law-making process can be applied in the space law context. In the absence of such safeguards, it is essential that the courts act as a safety net that protects against the limitations of bureaucracy.

Flexibility is also a key feature of common law. Indeed, Carbello has suggested that this flexibility in the context of a fast-moving legal environment is one of the reasons why Dubai chose to adopt common law in 2006.¹⁸ Flexibility will likely prove highly important for space law. It is impossible for Earth-bound lawyers to anticipate every eventuality that will arise in space. There will inevitably be gaps and inconsistencies. Therefore, the quality of decision making will be markedly better if judges are able to respond to practical situations. Consider, for example, *force majeure*. The English case of *Matsoukis v Priestman & Co* held that while industrial action can count as *force majeure*, bad weather cannot.¹⁹ Legislators are not currently in a position now to make evidence-backed determinations of the existence and scope of hazards in space. This can only be informed by the facts of specific cases. Judges should not be hamstrung by rigid constraints of national codes that purport to provide a comprehensive set of rules.

3.2 *Elevating the quality of debate*

Structures within common law promote a healthy dialogue between judges, legislatures, and academics. A key reason for this is that laws can be tested out and the fairness of judgments carefully analysed. This was well illustrated in the saga of UK tort litigation concerning asbestos-related injury. In order to preserve

¹² Colin B. Picker, 'International Law's Mixed Heritage: A Common/Civil Law Jurisdiction' (2008) 41 *Vanderbilt Journal of Transnational Law* 4, at 1101.

¹³ Space Law Committee of the International Law Association, 'Draft Convention on the Settlement of Space Law Disputes adopted by the Space Law Committee of the International Law Association' (1998) *International Outer Space Law*, Volume 7, Part 3, at 734.

¹⁴ *Statute of the International Court of Justice*, Article 59.

¹⁵ Deak (n 6).

¹⁶ [1967] 2 All ER 1197.

¹⁷ *Ibid.* at 1202.

¹⁸ Alejandro Carballo, 'The Law of the Dubai International Financial Centre: Common Law Oasis or Mirage Within the UAE?' (2007) 21 *Arab Law Quarterly* 1, at 99.

¹⁹ [1915] 1 K.B. 681.

consistency in the (non-statutory) law of causation, the House of Lords in *Barker v Corus*²⁰ handed down a decision that significantly restricted the ability of victims of asbestos exposure to recover damages. The UK Parliament responded rapidly to public pressure to create an exception to the normal rules of causation for asbestos.²¹ This achieved a well-balanced outcome that preserved clear rules of causation whilst ensuring that asbestos victims were able to recover damages for negligence. Such a solution would not have been foreseeable in advance of the litigation. It is only by stress-testing rules and developing doctrines accordingly that the law can properly respond to the needs of litigating parties.

The best way to test whether a law will function well or not is to test if it survives contact with reality. The folly of formulating law without consideration for practical concerns was highlighted by the German legal theorist Rudolph von Jhering. He posited the existence of the ‘Begriffshimmel’ – a heaven of juristic concepts far removed from the real world.²² The thought experiment set out the idea that effective laws cannot be formulated in the abstract. Common law jurisdictions all demonstrate a strong commitment to law reporting. By contrast, civil law jurisdictions often do not have official law reporting.²³ These are practices which would, if applied to the space law context, contribute to an ongoing process of refinement.

3.3 Inclusive Space Law

It is vital that the development of space law should be able to take into account views from all across the world. It is here that one of the biggest concerns with the civil law method of space law making emerges. If the world develops a space law regime formulated by major players such as the US, China, the EU, and the UK, then there is a real risk that the opinions of swathes of humankind will be ignored. Henrich has argued that there are many moral judgments upon which people in Western countries reach different conclusions to the rest of the world. He notes, for example, the importance of *mens rea* in determining blameworthiness.²⁴ Specifically, he states that individuals in Western countries tend to describe someone as less blameworthy if they lacked intent.²⁵ This is just a small demonstration of a wider problem; imposing substantial law of a certain character is an insult to countries who wield less diplomatic clout. In common law, attitudes from numerous countries are pooled and considered. There are countless English private law cases where the law from countries including Canada, Australia, and the US, is examined, analysed, and applied or not according to consideration of all the necessary factors. For example, the UK Supreme Court in *Patel v Mirza*²⁶ discussed at length the judgment of the Supreme Court of Canada (SCR) in *Hall v Hebert*,²⁷ referring to the explanation that McLachlin J gave for the rationale behind the illegality defence.²⁸ This demonstrates that common law enables judges to draw on an international wealth of thinking. For example, in *Barlow v Clowes*,²⁹ an English trusts case, there was substantial discussion as to whether the “North American” method of recovering assets in bankruptcy should be used. The Court of Appeal decided not to adopt the North American approach – concluding that the complications involved in implementing that approach were too great.³⁰

²⁰ [2006] UKHL 20.

²¹ Compensation Act 2006, s.3. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2006/29/contents>

²² Rudolf von Jhering, ‘Im juristischen Begriffshimmel’, ‘Von Jhering, Scherz Und Ernst In Der Jurisprudenz’ (11th ed. 1912), 245.

²³ Deak (n 6), at 341.

²⁴ Joseph P. Henrich, *The weirdest people in the world: How the west became psychologically peculiar and particularly prosperous* (Penguin Books 2021).

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ [2016] UKSC 42.

²⁷ [1993] 2 SCR 159.

²⁸ (n 20), [59]

²⁹ [1992] 4 All ER 22.

³⁰ *Ibid.* at 43.

This style of judgment greatly enhances the quality of debate. It ensures that domestic laws are properly considered and compared to alternatives. It also gives courts a much larger pool of expertise and knowledge to draw upon in formulating the law. By contrast, a civil law approach risks creating lawyers who are experts in their narrow jurisdictions but cannot think beyond. An approach that takes into account non-major countries is particularly important given the need to avoid perpetuating colonial attitudes – or even creating new ones. Van Eijk and Aganaba argue that in decolonising international law, it is not enough to simply include countries such as those in Africa in discussions about space law.³¹ They must have power to actually influence law-making. For example, perhaps there should be a single international court that should have jurisdiction over disputes between countries in space. It should draw upon legal expertise from across the world by being staffed by a diverse judiciary.

4. ADDRESSING CONCERNS

4.1 Uncertainty

The main argument against such a common law approach is purported uncertainty. The argument runs as follows: 1) legal certainty is a prerequisite for private entities being willing to engage in the space activities, 2) a civil law approach is better at achieving legal certainty, therefore, 3) a common law approach will stifle space innovation. This argument is important. Hart, for example, argues that the most important purpose that law serves is “providing guides to human conduct”.³² Applying this argument to space law rests on the premise that certainty is best achieved by setting out clear rules from the outset. This argument can be countered by noting that legal certainty has more to do with the substance of the law, not the structure. To take an example from the law of contract, many commercial entities value English law for the legal certainty it delivers. In particular, the lack of a general requirement of good faith. The fact that England is a common law jurisdiction and France is a civil law jurisdiction is not the reason why England has no requirement of good faith,³³ yet France has one.³⁴ Indeed, the fact that common law fosters dialogue between Parliament, courts, academics, and judges may be one of the reasons why England has retained this aspect of its contract law which is seen by some as a crucial aspect of the popularity of the UK as a place to do business. By giving judges law-making powers, they may feel a greater sense of responsibility. For example, in *Re Spectrum Plus Ltd*,³⁵ the House of Lords acknowledged that “[t]he commercial life of [the United Kingdom] depends upon the reliability of the security arrangements that are entered into between debtors and their creditors”.³⁶ Judges therefore feel a great weight of responsibility to minimise secondary consequences of their judgments.

Even if it is conceded that the structure of law has some role to play in affecting legal certainty, it does not necessarily follow that the structure of common law is ill-suited at achieving legal certainty. Courts are frequently confronted with novel situations where the law may be incomplete. Yet they resolve cases by using well-established legal principles.³⁷ Perhaps legislators could begin by setting out general principles and then develop more substantive law as specific issues arise. For example, the principle of *nemo dat quod*

³¹ Cristian van Eijk and Timiebi Aganaba, ‘Inspired by Africa: A New Approach to Global Space Governance’ (2021) 9 *New Space* 1, at 1-4.

³² HLA Hart, Joseph Raz and Penelope A. Bulloch, *The Concept of Law* (3rd edn, OUP 2012), at 249.

³³ See, e.g., *Walford v Miles*, [1992] 2 AC 128.

³⁴ *Code Civil*, Article 1104.

³⁵ [2005] 2 AC 680.

³⁶ *Ibid.* at 706.

³⁷ Ronald Dworkin, *Law’s Empire* (1st ed, Hart 1998), at 19.

non habet could provide an important basis for judges to formulate more substantive space property law upon.

4.2 The inadequacy of customary international law

The most striking aspect of the development of space law in response to events – not abstract theory – is the rapid formation of the rule of customary international law of freedom of movement into outer space. For example, Judge Lachs in the *North Sea Continental Shelf Case*³⁸ noted the rule was established “within a remarkably short period of time”. General practice and *opinio juris* were rapidly established after “the launching States sought no permission, nor did the other States protest.” Judge Lachs uses this as an example to demonstrate the fact that law must respond to “the great acceleration of social and economic change, combined with that of science and technology”.³⁹ Is custom adequate for progressive development or is it necessary for there to be an international space court with universal and supreme jurisdiction that can develop rules according to *stare decisis*? Arguably, in its current form, rules on the development of customary international law are inadequate to meet the demands of space law. In particular, this is because of the contradiction inherent in the *opinio juris* requirement; custom can only arise after states have acted in a certain way “based on their being conscious of having a duty to” act or abstain.⁴⁰ Perhaps such a formulation was a pragmatic way to identify custom when international law was ill-defined and protean. But in the 21st century, such an approach is woefully ill-suited to reflecting the dominant role that positive law plays compared to natural law. A good illustration of this can be seen by analysing the treatment of the ILC Draft Articles on the Immunity of State officials from foreign criminal jurisdiction. In particular, Article 7 was criticised for not being *lex lata*.⁴¹ The ILC is in an impossible position; it is very difficult to progressively develop the law through custom when international law rules are so well documented that the *opinio juris* fiction is nigh-on impossible to achieve in practice. Another problem with customary international law is the exemption that exists for persistent objectors.⁴² It would be unfeasible for only some states to be bound by international norms in space. A court of compulsory, supreme jurisdiction would resolve this problem; disunity will breed distrust and make international law-making impossible.

5. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper has not been to argue the superiority of common law over civil law. Rather, it has sought to challenge what appear to be orthodox positions that have taken hold in space jurisprudence. The key point has been to argue that the current focus of academics and legislators should be to ask less ‘what should the law be?’ and more ‘how should legal systems be structured to respond to the ongoing legal issues that will arise in relation to space law?’. By analysing common law methodology, it has been argued that valuable lessons can be learned that might elevate the quality of debate and improve law-making.

³⁸ *North Sea Continental Shelf (Federal Republic of Germany/Netherlands)*, [1969] ICJ 1.

³⁹ *Ibid.* at 230.

⁴⁰ *Lotus case, (France v. Turkey) (1927) P.C.I.J., Ser. A, No. 10*, [76] (Majority opinion).

⁴¹ Rosanne van Alebeek, ‘The “International Crime” Exception in the ILC Draft Articles on the Immunity of State Officials from Foreign Criminal Jurisdiction: Two Steps Back?’ (2018) *AJIL Unbound*, at 27.

⁴² See, e.g., *Colombia v Peru, ‘Asylum Case’*, [1950] ICJ 6 278.